

Efficient cathode for the hydrogen evolution reaction in alkaline membrane water electrolysis based on NiCoP embedded in carbon fibres

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Direct preparation of cathode for membrane alkaline water electrolysis.
- NiCoP/carbon fiber cathode with high catalytic activity prepared.
- The carbon precursor influenced the electrode surface area and catalyst particle size.
- Excellent stability achieved during 120 h test at 400 mA cm⁻².

ABSTRACT

Porous carbon nano/microfibres (PCFs) modified by NiCoP nanoparticles (NiCoP/CF) were tested as gas diffusion cathodes in a zero-gap alkaline water electrolyser. Two types of precursors were used for the preparation of carbon fibres by needle-less spinning: polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and a combination of PAN and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). The influence of the selected precursors on the morphology, porosity, and surface area of the carbon fibres was examined. Both samples NiCoP/CF_PAN and NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP were characterised by means of (i) structural and phase composition, (ii) catalytic activity for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), and (iii) performance and stability under membrane alkaline water electrolysis (MAWE) conditions. The more porous, yet stable fibres of the NiCoP/CF_PAN outperformed the NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP cathode. Nevertheless, both cathodes achieved high activity comparable to the Ni electrode modified by Pt/C catalyst, as well as exceptional stability for long-term intermittent electrolysis under MAWE conditions.

1. Introduction

With the interest in renewable energy sources (RES) and in the decarbonization of industry rapidly accelerating, water electrolysis can now be regarded as a key technology enabling efficient energy conversion and storage. Since energy efficiency, flexibility, and robustness, coupled with economic viability, represent crucial criteria for the successful application of hydrogen technologies, there is an urgent need for low cost and stable cathodes capable of efficient hydrogen production [1]. The reason is that the overpotential related to the kinetics of the electrode reactions represents an important contribution to the efficiency losses of energy conversion.

An alkaline environment is suitable for a vast range of materials with satisfactory electrochemical activity and chemical stability under operating conditions [2–4]. On the other hand, the cathode reaction, i. e., hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), is much more complex compared to an acidic environment, slowing down the kinetics of the electrode reaction. The generally accepted HER mechanism includes

energy-intensive water dissociation and adsorption of hydrogen atoms on free catalytic sites of the electrode surface, eq. (1). This is followed by the electrochemical and/or chemical processes of hydrogen production, eqs. (2) and (3), respectively [5–7]. Another factor influencing the reaction kinetics is the undesirable adsorption of OH⁻ ions, which can block the active sites otherwise used for water adsorption [8]. These factors result in higher HER overpotentials in alkaline media compared to acidic media. It is, therefore, essential to find an optimal non-platinum group metal-based material able to effectively overcome these limitations.

Nickel- and cobalt-based alloys, sulphides, selenides, carbides, and phosphides belong to the most investigated groups of materials as

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electrocatalysts for the HER in an alkaline environment [2,3,9–13]. Although the majority of the materials tested still do not achieve catalytic activity comparable to Pt metals, their lower cost and, conversely, the scarcity of precious metals makes the transition metal-based catalysts more suitable for large-scale applications [2]. A recently published review of non-platinum electrocatalysts in alkaline media revealed that phosphide-based materials represent one of the most promising candidates for HER electrocatalysts due to their relatively high electronic conductivity and catalytic activity [9]. The main reasons proposed for the enhanced activity are as follows:

- (i) The partially negative P atoms are able to weaken the H–OH bond, thus enhancing the water dissociation and subsequent adsorption of H atoms [14].
- (ii) In contrast to metal sulphides and selenides, in the case of phosphides the HER is not limited to the sites of crystal edges, but can also proceed on the bulk material surface [9].
- (iii) With a suitable atomic ratio of P and metal, the metal phosphides can exhibit excellent electronic conductivity [15].

Nickel- and cobalt-based phosphides are considered the most investigated members of this group [15–21]. Moreover, the materials based on bimetallic NiCoP proved to be highly active catalysts [14,22–24]. According to Zhang et al. [14], the reason for the high activity can be ascribed to the synergistic effect between Ni, Co, and P. Ni and P enhance water dissociation while Co facilitates the recombination of adsorbed H atoms into H₂. Such a catalyst is able to drive the current density of 10 mA cm⁻² at a very low overpotential of 58 mV in a 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution [14].

In addition to the catalyst material, the choice of a catalyst support plays a crucial role in terms of high geometric area, electronic conductivity, and stability – properties required for commercial electrodes [25, 26]. In this respect, nickel is the first choice as it meets all demands and, in addition, it shows relatively good HER activity by itself [27,28]. However, under HER conditions, a non-conductive hydride layer can form, thus increasing the contact resistance between the Ni substrate and the deposited catalyst layer.

Carbon is the material traditionally used as a catalyst support for the hydrogen electrode in PEM fuel cells, as well as in PEM water electrolysis. It is typically used in the form of carbon black. Its main advantages consist in chemical inertness, satisfactory electronic conductivity, and high specific surface. An innovative approach is the use of a carbon catalyst support in the form of fibres (CFs) [29]. Carbon in fibre form offers several significant advantages. The most important ones are as follows:

- (i) hierarchical structure ensuring a high, easily accessible specific surface of the support,
- (ii) high electronic conductivity due to the partially graphitised structure originating from the heat treatment of the material and due to the fibre form reducing the contact resistance between the individual particles, and
- (iii) incorporation of the catalyst into the bulk of the CF volume ensuring its high stability on the support and at the same time good electronic contact.

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and petroleum pitch are the most frequently used precursors in industry for CF preparation [30,31]. The manufacturing process generally consists of the following steps:

- (i) preparation of the corresponding polymer precursor solution,
- (ii) fibre spinning using electrostatic and mechanical forces, and
- (iii) thermal treatment - stabilisation, carbonisation and (optional) graphitisation to obtain CFs with the desired properties [31].

In particular, porous carbon nano/microfibrils (PCFs) in energy

conversion and storage devices have attracted much attention as they can be processed with a high surface area and with suitable mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties [29,31–33]. Needle-less electrospinning technology (NLE) offers a cost-effective and versatile method to produce such PCFs [32,33]. The basic principle and methodology of NLE have already been covered by many researchers [29,33,34]. The main advantage of this technique is the ability to produce continuous, defect-free fibres from numerous solution jets generated from the polymer bath. This pre-empts the mass yield limitation that occurs in the needle electrospinning process using only one liquid polymer jet reservoir in a longitudinal electric field [33,35]. After appropriate thermal treatment, such PCFs exhibited sufficient HER catalytic activity in an acidic environment, an overpotential of 280 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², as well as acceptable stability even under mild anodic polarisation. Stability was determined by cyclic voltammetry within the electrode potential range of –400 to 200 mV vs RHE for 500 cycles [33]. Furthermore, by adding Ni or Co salts and H₃PO₄ to the electrospinning bath during PCF preparation, it is possible during the heat treatment to form nanoparticles of the corresponding phosphides in the fibre structure resulting in a material with high catalytic activity [36,37].

The aim of the presented work is to develop a gas diffusion cathode based on PCFs modified by NiCoP nanoparticles (NiCoP/CF) in a zero-gap alkaline water electrolyser and to perform a detailed characterisation of the performance of this innovative material in the anion-exchange membrane water electrolysis process. To achieve this target, two types of NiCoP/CF electrodes using different precursors for the preparation of the carbon fibres were tested. NiCoP/CF_PAN was prepared from the PAN precursor and NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP was prepared from PAN and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) precursors. The influence of the selected precursors on the morphology, porosity, and surface area of the carbon fibres resulting after polymer thermal decomposition were examined. Both samples were characterised by means of:

- (i) structural and phase composition,
- (ii) catalytic activity for the HER,
- (iii) performance and stability under membrane alkaline water electrolysis (MAWE) conditions.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Cathode material

The NiCoP/CF catalysts were prepared by NLE technology from precursor solutions consisting of metal salts (Sigma-Aldrich, p. a.), polymers: polyacrylonitrile (PAN, Mw = 150 000 g mol⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, Mw = 55 000 g mol⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich), and H₃PO₄ (Merck 85%) according to Table 1. All components were dissolved and homogenised in 30 ml *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, Acros Organic, 99.8%). The NanospiderTM NS LAB (Elmarco, Czech Republic) was used for the spinning process with the following setting: the spinning distance ca. 185 mm, rotation speed of the spinning electrode 9 rpm, high voltage cca. 75 kV and the induced current between electrodes was 100 mA. The prepared polymeric fibres were subjected to a heat treatment process in an Ar atmosphere followed by sintering in a reducing environment. To obtain uniform catalytic layers, the polymeric fibre foam was sintered in-between two Al₂O₃ plates. 2 × 2 cm² parts were cut from the sintered layers and used as a cathode.

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD, PhilipsX' PertPro, CuKα radiation) was used for phase identification of phosphide nanoparticles. The structure and morphology were observed by a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-7000F, JEOL, Japan, equipped with EDX analyser) and a transmission electron microscope (TEM and HRTEM, JEM-2100F, JEOL, Japan, equipped with an INCA X-ray microanalysis system). The Raman spectroscopy was measured by HORIBA – XploRA ONE, France. The porosity and specific surface area were measured with respect to

Table 1
The composition of NiCoP/CF catalyst precursors with heat treatment condition.

Sample	NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O (g)	CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O (g)	PAN (g)	PVP (g)	SDS (g)	H ₃ PO ₄ (μl)	Atmosphere (°C)
NiCoP/CF PAN	1.2	1.2	3			300	Ar 1000/H ₂ 780
NiCoP/CF PAN-PVP	1.2	1.2	3	3.6	1	300	Ar 1000/H ₂ 780

BET isotherms NOVA 1200e surface area & pore size analyzer (Quantachrome Instruments, USA).

The contents of Ni and Co in the resulting fibrous samples were determined by means of atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS), performed using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer).

For comparison purposes, (i) bare nickel foam (pore size 580 μm, INCO Advanced Technology Materials (Dalian) Co., Ltd, 2 × 2 cm²) and (ii) nickel foam modified by a Pt/C (40 wt %) catalyst (1 mg Pt/C cm⁻²) fixed to the substrate by a poly (styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) copolymer (PSEBS) with 1,4-diazabicyclo [2.2.2]octane (DABCO) functional groups anion-selective binder (0.08 mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm⁻²) were used as cathodes. All cathodes were used without further modifications.

2.2. Anode material

A nickel foam (2 × 2 cm² of geometric area) modified by an IrO₂ catalyst (1.5 mg IrO₂ cm⁻²) fixed to the substrate by a 0.08 mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm⁻² was used as an anode during the water electrolysis tests. One exception was the long-term stability test where pure Ni foam was used to avoid any potential interference of an anode with the development of the cathode properties over time.

2.3. Membrane alkaline water electrolysis

The prepared electrodes were tested in a laboratory alkaline water electrolyser in a two-electrode arrangement. An anion-selective PSEBS-CM-DABCO polymer membrane (60 μm thick) was used as a separator between the anode and cathode compartments. Details of the membrane properties can be found elsewhere [38]. The current collectors were made of gold-plated nickel plates. The electrolytic cell body was made of poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) compressed by duralumin end-plates using a constant torque of 3 Nm. The laboratory electrolyser was operated in continuous flow-by mode. The flow rate of the liquid electrolyte was 25 ml min⁻¹.

The potentiostatic load curves were measured using KOH solutions of 0.1 and 1 mol dm⁻³ as a liquid electrolyte at 50 °C in a voltage range of 1.5–2.0 V (with a step of 0.05 V). The relatively low concentrations of the electrolyte were chosen with the aim to increase the flexibility of the electrolysis and to test the novel electrode under near pH-neutral conditions. The set value of the cell voltage was maintained for 60 s and the current passing through the cell was recorded. The steady-state values of the current were averaged and used to calculate the current density corresponding to the given cell voltage. Each load curve was measured three times for at least two different samples of the same cathode to verify data reproducibility. The presented graphs show the average values of all measurements along with the error bars.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was used to separate the ohmic resistance of the cell and the kinetics of the electrode reactions. The EIS spectra were recorded at a constant cell voltage of 1.8 V. A perturbing signal amplitude of 30 mV and a frequency range of 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz were used. Evaluation of the spectra was performed using an equivalent circuit consisting of two parallel CPE-Rp elements (constant phase elements CPE 1,2 and polarisation resistances R1,2 for the process with the two time constants), series-connected inductance, and cell ohmic resistance (Rcell) (see Fig. S1 in supporting information). Since it is difficult to exactly determine the active area of the porous electrode with the multiatom catalyst, the Rcell, R1 and R2 values are presented as

their absolute values (Ohm).

A stability test (>100 h) was performed in a galvanostatic regime at a current density of 400 mA cm⁻² in 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution at 50 °C. To verify the stability even for intermittent electrolysis, the constant polarisation was interrupted every 5 h for a short period of time. During the intermission, load curves and EIS spectra were measured to identify any degradation processes that might have occurred. Water was supplied to the system during the experiment to maintain a constant electrolyte concentration.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. NiCoP/CF cathode

3.1.1. Structural characterisation

The SEM and TEM images of the composite catalyst material prepared, shown in Fig. 1, reveal precise fibrous structures for both NiCoP/CF samples (Fig. 1A to E). The annealing process in Ar and subsequent reduction in H₂ atmosphere led to the formation of a porous structure in a carbon matrix due to the spillover of H₂ molecules into carbon fibres. This effect was discussed in detail in a previous study [33]. The porous fibrous structure is clearly evident on the SEM cross-section of the fibres (Fig. 1 B,E) and on the TEM images at the end of the fibres (Fig. 1 C, F). The homogeneous distribution of NiCoP nanoparticles is clearly visible in both types of prepared fibres. Nevertheless, it was found that the size of the catalyst particles formed is influenced by the polymer precursor used. When PAN was used, the catalytic particle size distribution ranged from 50 to 200 nm. In the case of the PAN/PVP precursor, the distribution is more narrow, ranging from 30 to 100 nm with a distinct maximum in the range of 30–50 nm (see histogram in Fig. S2 for supporting information). The multi-layered graphene shell was proved to cover all NiCoP nanoparticles formed (for detailed HR-TEM images, see Fig. S3 in supporting information). This is in good agreement with the results obtained from Raman spectra (Fig. 2C). This is an interesting aspect. The graphene shell may help to protect catalyst particles from degradation. At the same time, a synergistic effect similar to Ref. [39] cannot be excluded here.

The elemental composition determined by SEM-EDS analysis shows that the catalyst particles contain the corresponding elements in a ratio of approximately 1:1:1, indicating the desired elemental composition of the catalyst phase. AAS analysis revealed an overall higher concentration of metals in the NiCoP/CF PAN sample compared to the NiCoP/CF PAN-PVP sample, suggesting a proportionally higher ratio of catalytically active particles towards the carbon support, see Table 2. Furthermore, according to BET analysis, the sample prepared from the PAN precursor exhibited a higher external surface (78.4 m² g⁻¹) than the PAN-PVP sample (38.6 m² g⁻¹).

The phase composition of the samples was determined by means of X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), see Fig. 2A. Pure diffraction peaks for the NiCoP bimetallic phosphide (space group P 62m, a = 5.834 Å) can be well indexed according to JCPDS card no. 71–2336. These peaks located at 40.01°, 44.99°, 47.64°, 54.46°, 54.86°, and 55.26° can be indexed to the (111), (201), (210), (300), (002), and (211) crystal planes of NiCoP, respectively [40]. The crystal structures of NiCoP nanoparticles adopt a hexagonal Fe₂P structure as shown in the scheme on Fig. 2B. Two broad diffraction peaks at 23.86° and 43.27° belong to the amorphous carbon matrix of NiCoP/CF fibres and can be clearly assigned to the XRD pattern of bare carbon fibres (black line in Fig. 2A) [37]. Another broad signal at 11.74° can be assigned as graphitic carbon (GC) [41]. Surprisingly, GC

Fig. 1. SEM (A, B, C, D) and TEM (E, F) images of the NiCoP/CF_PAN (left column) and NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP cathodes (right column).

was not detected in bare CF. This implies that the addition of metal salts and phosphoric acid leads to the formation of multilayered graphene. The presence of GC was also verified by Raman spectra (Fig. 2C) where both characteristic signals D band (disordered carbon) and G band (graphitic carbon) were observed [42]. The ratios of ID/IG and IG'/IG for the NiCoP carbon fibrous samples prepared from PAN or PAN-PVP precursors were 0.64 and 0.42, respectively. These values suggest the existence of a multilayer graphene structure and the same value of IG'/IG ratio for both samples indicates a very similar number of layers in GC structures. No significant differences in the diffractograms recorded are visible for the CF prepared from the PAN and PAN-PVP precursors. This confirms that the different polymer composition does not affect the final catalyst structure of the cathodes.

3.1.2. Alkaline water electrolysis

Load curves of the two electrolysis cells based on the NiCoP/CF cathodes prepared by means of two polymeric CF precursors in an alkaline environment are summarised in Fig. 3.

The results obtained clearly document the high catalytic activity of the PCF catalysts for the two KOH concentrations studied. Current loads at identical voltages reached significantly higher values for both cathodes studied compared to the bare Ni cathode. Remarkably, in a 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution, both samples surpassed the electrode with the state-of-the-art platinum catalyst. At both electrolyte concentrations under study, PCFs based on the PAN precursor outperformed PAN-PVP samples. The reason for this difference can be attributed primarily to the higher ratio of catalytically active particles towards the carbon support found in this material, as indicated by AAS, see Table 2. Another explanation is the higher surface area of the PAN sample already proven

Fig. 2. A: XRD patterns of NiCoP/CF produced by NLE from different precursors: PAN or combined PAN-PVP, B: illustration of hexagonal crystal structure of NiCoP with unit cell, C: Raman spectra of the NiCoP/CFs.

Table 2

Elemental composition of the NiCoP/CF samples determined by SEM-EDS and AAS.

Element	SEM-EDS		AAS	
	NiCoP/CF_PAN	NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP	NiCoP/CF_PAN	NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP
	At. %/%	At. %/%	Mol. %/%	Mol. %/%
Ni	3.2	2.8	55.2	61.8
Co	3.3	3.1	44.8	38.2
P	2.7	2.6	–	–
C	90.9	91.6	–	–

by BET. Since carbon itself is not the main catalytically active component, its higher porosity may contribute to the better access of the reactants to the catalyst itself. An increase in the KOH solution concentration from 0.1 to 1.0 mol dm⁻³ resulted in a general increase in the current load values. This behavior is expected, as the increasing KOH concentration, and thus conductivity, increase utilization of the three-dimensional structure of the cathode due to the improved ionic contact between the cathode and polymer electrolyte membrane. This explanation is proven by the shape of the load curves recorded for lower KOH concentration and shown in Fig. 3A. Here, the significant ohmic resistance hindering the electrolysis process for both NiCoP/CF catalysts

at higher current density is clearly visible. NiCoP/CF_PAN shows a lower extent of this hindrance.

To obtain a more detailed understanding of the behavior and differences between individual cathodes under alkaline water electrolysis conditions, the impedance spectra were measured and evaluated. Examples of typical EIS spectra are shown in Figs. S4 and S5. The parameters of the fitted equivalent circuit are summarised in Table 3. The parameter Rcell for both NiCoP/CF samples in 0.1 and 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH at a cell voltage of 1.8 V showed similar values close to 0.12 and 0.057 Ω, respectively. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the samples affecting the electrical conductivity. Moreover, at 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH, the R1 values for both samples are close to one another. Only the polarisation resistance R2 differs in both concentrations, and therefore affects the electrolytic cell performance for both NiCoP/CF samples. Since the same electrolyte concentration, the same separator, and the same anode with highly active IrO₂ catalyst were used for all measurements, in this particular case resistance R1 can be assigned to anode polarisation resistance. Consequently, R2 can be attributed to cathode polarisation resistance, as only the cathode differs in the experiments. This is rather contrary to the literature where, especially in acidic environments, the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) is considered the rate determining step [43]. This is due to the somehow complex reaction mechanism that consists of four electron transfer steps, including energy-intensive water molecule dissociation [44]. However,

Fig. 3. Load curves documenting the influence of the PAN and PAN-PVP precursors on cathode performance in A: 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH and B: 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH. Pure Ni foam and Ni foam modified by Pt/C are shown for comparison.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm²) – 1.5 mg IrO₂ cm⁻² + 0.08 mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm⁻²; KOH electrolyte; temperature – 50 °C. (No pre-treatment was applied.)

Table 3

Values of cell ohmic resistance (R_{cell}), polarisation resistance R₁, and R₂ in 0.1 and 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solutions. EIS were measured at 1.8 V.

Concentration of KOH/mol dm ⁻³	R _{cell} /Ω		R ₁ /Ω		R ₂ /Ω	
	0.1	1	0.1	1	0.1	1
NiCoP/CF_PAN	0.122	0.055	0.045	0.022	0.104	0.047
	±	±	±	±	±	±
NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.003	0.004
	±	±	±	±	±	±
Pt/C	0.119	0.059	-	0.028	0.214	0.071
	±	±	-	±	±	±
Ni foam	0.003	0.009	-	0.002	0.002	0.002
	±	±	-	±	±	±
Pt/C	0.169	0.074	-	-	0.128	0.047
	±	±	-	-	±	±
Ni foam	0.003	0.001	-	-	0.003	0.002
	±	±	-	-	±	±
Ni foam	0.159	0.067	-	-	-	0.280
	±	±	-	-	-	±
Ni foam	0.003	0.002	-	-	-	0.004
	±	±	-	-	-	±

as mentioned earlier in this paper, the situation in an alkaline environment is more complicated as the water molecule dissociation occurs at the cathode, thus hindering HER kinetics. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that in our particular system these effects, together with the use of a highly active IrO₂ anode catalyst, may lead to the change in the rate-determining step from OER to HER. It should be noted that, for the impedance spectrum of pure Ni foam and Ni foam modified by a Pt/C cathode catalyst, only one large semicircle could be identified and thus it was attributed to HER polarisation resistance.

In addition to the more conductive environment, the significantly better MAWE performance in a more concentrated KOH solution for both samples was also caused by the decreased HER polarisation resistance. As already mentioned, this can be attributed to improved ionic contact even for the active sites not in direct contact with the polymer electrolyte membrane. The lower catalyst content of the PAN-PVP electrode is more sensitive to the low liquid electrolyte concentration, as the concentration of the active centres is lower. In a less concentrated electrolyte, where the 3D structure is not fully utilised, it causes a higher current load on the active sites. Thus, the process is burdened by higher polarisation losses. This may be the reason why the HER polarisation resistance of NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP was reduced by almost a factor of three, while for the PAN sample it was only halved.

The situation with quantification of OER kinetic parameters is more problematic as the reaction proceeds on the IrO₂ catalyst relatively fast. Thus, the polarisation resistance of the OER proceeding on the IrO₂/Ni foam anode in connection with a NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP cathode in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH is burdened by a significant experimental error (46.6%). The impedance spectrum showed only an indication of a semicircle that could be more probably attributed to the double-layer effects of a porous electrode structure rather than to the OER polarisation resistance (see supporting information) [45].

EIS shows relatively high values of cell ohmic resistance. This is in agreement with the shape of the load curves indicating that, for a low concentrated KOH solution, the ohmic resistance is a rate-determining step, as discussed above. The highest value of R_{cell} was observed for the Ni foam modified by the Pt/C catalyst. This phenomenon is explained by the anion-selective binder used which, on the one hand, improves the ionic conductivity of the catalytic layer, on the other hand, however, acts as an electrical insulator [46].

According to a recently published review on membrane alkaline water electrolysis [47], the electrolytic cell with NiCoP/CF_PAN cathode exhibits remarkable activity above the 75th percentile of other comparable membrane electrolyzers under comparable conditions. To provide an example, the electrolytic cell utilising the precious metal IrO₂ and Pt/C catalysts exhibited current densities of 200 [48], 399 [49], and 1150 mA cm⁻² [50] at 1.8 V and 50 °C (cf. 422 and 355 mA cm⁻² for NiCoP/CF_PAN and NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP, respectively).

To determine the stability of the samples for intermittent electrolysis,

over 100-h stability tests were performed (Fig. 4) according to the procedure described in the Experimental section of this study. Each point in the figure corresponds to the average value of the cell voltage for individual 5-h periods. Both samples showed remarkable stability during the testing procedure. For the NiCoP/CF_PAN electrode, the overall voltage decreased from 2.04 V to 1.98 V (2.9%) with a slope of -0.43 mV h⁻¹. For the NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP electrode, the decrease was even more significant from 2.12 V to 2.04 V (3.6%). For the latter, two slopes (-1 mV h⁻¹ and -0.18 mV h⁻¹, respectively) can be distinguished during the measurement, suggesting that the activation and conditioning of the individual components of the electrolytic cell during the first approximately 60 h differs from standard degradation processes. Afterwards, it follows a similar trend (and thus the mechanism) to the NiCoP/CF_PAN electrode. The complete information on the development of the cell voltage values over time recorded for both stability tests is provided in the supporting information, Fig. S6.

Fig. 5 summarises the equivalent circuit parameters according to the EIS spectra and load curves recorded at the selected times of electrolysis (0, 28, 61, 96, and 115 h). For both samples, a continuing increase in cell ohmic resistance (R_{cell}) is visible. This can be explained by the gradual relaxation of the carbon fibres in the flowing electrolyte, changing the 3D cathode morphology and affecting the electronic contact of the catalytic layer to the membrane. Another explanation is the ongoing crumbling of the top layer of carbon fibres. This, on the one hand, affects the electrical contact, on the other hand it exposes additional active sites on the cathode surface to the liquid electrolyte solution. Finally, the third explanation, which was proposed in our previous report [51]. Briefly, in the zero-gap arrangement, both polymer and liquid electrolyte resistances contribute most to the overall cell ohmic resistance. Since the circulating KOH was partially exposed to air during the test, the continuous absorption of atmospheric CO₂ and the subsequent formation of carbonate anions reduces the conductivity of both electrolytes [52,53]. In reality, the interaction of all the above-mentioned aspects causes the changes observed, although the significance of the impact of the individual phenomena differs. For the NiCoP/CF_PAN sample, the minor decrease in polarisation resistance R₂ (cathode) along with the improving load curves suggests excellent stability of the cathode for long-term intermittent electrolysis with no indication of reduced activity. The observed decrease of R₂ can be attributed to the continuous minor activation of the electrode as well as to the possible crumbling of the carbon fibres. Additionally, the aforementioned gradual relaxation of the carbon fibres could lead to an increased filling of the pores with

Fig. 4. Intermittent stability test performed under MAWE conditions. Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm²) – Ni foam; electrolyte – 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH; temperature – 50 °C; current density – 400 mA cm⁻² (No pre-treatment was applied.).

Fig. 5. Fitted parameters of the EIS spectra of the water electrolysis process at 1.8 V (A, B) and load curves evaluated during the stability test (C, D). Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm²) – Ni foam; electrolyte – 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH; temperature – 50 °C; current density – 400 mA cm⁻² (No pre-treatment was applied.)

the electrolyte, resulting in improved utilization of the 3D structure of the electrode.

The better overall performance of the NiCoP/CF_PAN cathode, by means of (i) lower voltage recorded during the stability test, (ii) lower polarisation resistance R_2 with constant progression over time, and (iii) higher performance during the recording of the load curves, confirms the superior activity compared to the NiCoP/CF_PAN-PVP sample. This is consistent with previously measured load curves using an anode with IrO₂ catalyst (Fig. 3). Nevertheless, both samples exhibit equally exceptional and superior stability with no traces of degradation when compared to the results reported in the literature [54–57].

In order to verify that no degradation had occurred, XRD and SEM analyses of both samples before and after the stability test were performed (Fig. 6). No noticeable differences in the electrode phase composition but minor changes in CFs surface morphology are visible. The slightly different morphology pre- and post-stability test, especially for the NiCoP/CF_PAN, confirms the aforementioned theory of decreasing HER polarisation resistance due to (i) fibre relaxation caused by electrolyte penetration and (ii) crumbling of the top layer of the carbon fibres which revealed additional active sites on the cathode surface. For more details of sample morphology see supporting information Figs. S7 and S8. These results clearly show that both prepared samples exhibit very good stability. The catalyst does not change its composition during electrolysis. Moreover, the use of carbon fibres based on a PAN precursor as the support led to a gradual improvement of the cathode performance in the laboratory electrolyser.

4. Conclusion

The results presented in this study confirm the high catalytic activity of the NiCoP catalyst for the hydrogen evolution reaction in an alkaline environment. Incorporation of the catalyst nanoparticles on/in the carbon fibre support, formed by thermal decomposition of the electrospun polymeric precursors, represents a promising and suitable method of electrode preparation. Tests in an alkaline polymer electrolyte membrane cell have highlighted the significance of polymer precursor selection for the desired properties of the fibres. More porous, yet stable fibres originating from the heat treatment of polyacrylonitrile-based fibres outperformed the electrode based on sintered polyacrylonitrile – polyvinylpyrrolidone. This shows that a porous fibre structure allowing good access of water to the catalyst is preferential on condition that the resulting material retains sufficient electronic conductivity and mechanical stability. However, further research is needed to optimise the electrode materials' composition and the electrode structure.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martin Ďurovič: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Jaromír Hnát:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Magdaléna Strečková:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Karel Bouzek:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Fig. 6. Comparison by means of XRD analysis and SEM of NiCoP/CF PAN and NiCoP/CF PAN-PVP samples before MAWE (lower red spectra, SEM images in the first row) and after MAWE (upper blue spectra, SEM images in the second row). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.232506>.

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